

Instrument 2 (Model)

Name: _____ Date: _____
Course: _____ Start time: _____
Enrollment: _____ End time: _____

1. The goal is to develop a data model for a generic company. This company is made up of several departments of various types and with different characteristics, with employees working directly in the departments. Employees are differentiated by aspects inherent to their area of activity (e.g. area of operation and CREA number for engineers, CRC record for accountants, CNH number and vehicle for driver, etc.). Employees can also supervise any other of their peers. In this environment, several projects are carried out, which are controlled by a department. Projects have description and possibly other sensitive data. The projects are developed by several employees. In addition, projects require materials, which must have a detailed description and, if applicable, the validity record. The materials used by the projects come from suppliers, who have a CNPJ, trade name and contact phone number. It is important that each supply has a date of completion and an associated value, thus maintaining the purchase history.